

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TECHNIQUES AND PROCESSES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION AND MASTERY

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Study in Support of Foreign Language Learning

Abstract

This article explores the intricate processes and effective techniques involved in the acquisition and mastery of foreign languages. It delves into both passive and active learning methods, emphasizing the importance of transforming passive vocabulary knowledge into active usage through consistent practice in speaking and writing. The study highlights various techniques such as listening, reading, dialogue, and the use of technical aids, which align with natural learning processes and enhance language proficiency. The goal is to achieve a high level of language proficiency, including understanding all word meanings and speaking without an accent.

Keywords: foreign language acquisition, vocabulary mastery, passive learning, active learning, language techniques, listening and reading comprehension, dialogue practice

1. Introduction

Learning and mastering a foreign language is a long-term process that requires considerable effort and rational action on the part of both the student and the teacher. Vocabulary and grammar, the two main categories of knowledge in a foreign language, accumulate, develop, and maintain over time. Academics can obtain the most in-depth knowledge of the language, but this is not sufficient for its active and successful use. In addition to knowledge, active use of a foreign language requires skills.

Language is a skill similar to the ability to walk, balance, ride a bicycle, work with tools, or play musical instruments. Human consciousness integrates language, a learned skill. Language appears to be the result of a man's intellectual development and his desire to communicate with the world around him. While we speak language, communication occurs between individuals. People speak language, but they can also communicate through gestures, facial expressions, voice tones and intonation, touch, gaze, eye contact, or various forms of written language. Human progress and indirect contact with foreign languages have led to changes in communication methods. A person learns his native language in a natural way, but his literary improvement takes place in school at a certain age and mature. One can learn other languages in a similar way to learning one's mother tongue. The possibilities of human genius are great, which is why many people speak more than one foreign language.

The ability to master a foreign language is a different category of human quality. This skill necessitates a genetic predisposition and the accumulation of basic knowledge, which individuals master and transform into skills through practice. People acquire various skills such as moving by walking or swimming, riding a bicycle, using a work tool, playing a musical instrument, reading, writing, etc. In summary, mastering a

foreign language involves two categories of human abilities: knowledge and skills. In principle, we can acquire and develop these two human qualities together or separately.

Learning foreign languages has always been a challenge that scientists from various fields of science have dealt with. According to pedagogy, the study and mastery of foreign languages are considered at three levels:

- **Approaches:** According to Brown, H. D., & Lee, H. (2015) The text delves into the theoretical viewpoints and convictions surrounding teaching, language acquisition, learners, institutional and social concerns, course goals, and the applicability of these elements in a specific educational environment. [1] This publication examines the basic knowledge of the human mind, as well as its peculiarities and abilities to acquire a foreign language.

- **Methods** refer to the ways in which we apply the principles. A series of methods that have evolved over time mark the history of language teaching, according to Brown and Lee (2015). [2] According to Anthony (1963), method is the second of three hierarchical elements: approach, which is a set of assumptions about language, learning, and teaching; method, which is a comprehensive plan for the systematic presentation of a language course based on a chosen approach; and techniques, which are specific activities included in a curriculum that are consistent with method and in harmony with approach. [3] Today, these terms are still in common use among language teachers, but with different definitions. The post-method era encourages language teachers to focus on a 'pedagogy of particularity', focusing on learners, objectives, context, and social environment. Larsen-Freeman and Anderson (2011) echo Bell's definition of method as "techniques that realize a set of principles or goals" and offer practical solutions to problems in a particular teaching context. [4]

- **Techniques:** These are the ways teachers practice their teaching methods in the classroom during lessons. There are certain similarities and significant differences between the study and acquisition of the native language and foreign languages, which arise primarily from the ways and times of acquiring the relevant knowledge and skills. Regardless of whether the language is native or foreign, its acquisition basically takes place in a natural way, embedded in human genetics.

In the acquisition of foreign language knowledge and its transformation into foreign language skills, different methods are used, which are based on principles, and the methods themselves are applied through different techniques to the learners in the classrooms.

The process of studying, learning, and mastering a foreign language involves several successive stages, known as foreign language acquisition processes. This process also determines the various levels of proficiency in the foreign language. We view learning, acquisition, and mastery as distinct and sequential processes that involve the acquisition of vocabulary and grammar. In principle, acquiring vocabulary is the leading and most difficult part of learning a foreign language.

2. Research methodology

The results of a survey, conducted using questionnaires distributed in a special Facebook group, support the research on the topic. We distribute these surveys to the international community of polyglots, philologists, translators, foreign language teachers, and foreign language learners.

3. The unconscious acquisition of foreign words occurs through listening and reading comprehension

This mode of absorption is effortless. When the foreign language learner finds the text's content engaging and interesting, it can be an enjoyable and fun experience. The use of the words in the text aids in understanding their application, which is another advantage. In this type of acquisition, the learner comprehends the word's meaning within the context of what they hear or read. All of this engages the learner's logical thinking, which assimilates the word in a way that stimulates its memorization.

4. Conscious learning of foreign words can be achieved through repeated writing and speaking, or alternative methods such as using flash cards.

This approach necessitates exertion, leading to fatigue and distraction, both of which have detrimental effects. This method has other disadvantages, such as the loss of useful preparation time. However, these ways of learning foreign vocabulary give good results that can be reinforced, and in addition, the studied vocabulary is used in exercises with the aim of good memorization.

5. Processes for passive acquisition of foreign words.

Learning begins with the initial acquaintance with the foreign language, especially with the vocabulary in its natural form, presented verbally, as well as in an artificial form by writing with the letters of the corresponding alphabet. Learning a foreign language also includes grammar, which is the connecting link between

words and determines their order. Grammar expands the temporal dimensions of thought. The level of knowledge is relevant to language mastery because mastery involves not only knowledge but also the ability to use that knowledge effectively. The acquisition of the foreign language is a skill necessary for its use, i.e., absorption is a type of activation of what has been learned. Therefore, we can conclude that the acquisition of foreign vocabulary occurs in stages, in five main phases:

5.1. Recognizing foreign words without understanding their meaning.

With the recognition of foreign words, the initial process of learning the foreign language begins. For good recognition of foreign words, it is necessary to hear them several times before moving on to the next stage of their acquisition. This initial stage of learning foreign words is critical for developing correct pronunciation. Learning foreign words has two sides. Pronunciation and writing of the foreign language under study constitute one aspect, while their meaning and application constitute the other. The first stage consists only of recognizing words in speech. To achieve this goal, it is necessary for the foreign language learner to develop the ability to hear and clearly perceive the pronunciation of individual words.

5.2. Understanding the meaning of foreign words in context is considered the initial phase of passive mastery of foreign vocabulary, where the ability to actively use foreign words in speaking or writing has not yet been developed. In natural (implicit) learning of foreign words, they are first understood in context, and understanding of their exact meaning occurs when the foreign word is encountered several times in a different context. The same result can be achieved through situational perception of the foreign language, when heard foreign words are associated with specific objects or actions that are part of the situation at the time of using the foreign word or expression. In intensive learning (explicitly) of a foreign language with the help of a teacher, this process of learning the exact meaning of a foreign word can be accelerated by using a dictionary or being communicated by the teacher. A similar situation can occur when the independent user of a foreign language encounters an unfamiliar word. In such a case, the unknown foreign can be understood in context or translated with a dictionary. The difference between the two types of understanding is essential, because in the implicit method the learner arrives at the meaning of the unknown word through logical thinking, and in the explicit method the meaning of the word is taken from the dictionary, without logical thinking on the part of the learner. This difference affects the retention rate. Usually, implicit learning of foreign words takes longer. The disadvantage of explicit learning of foreign words is compensated by their repetition through listening or reading comprehension. The level of fluency in these words is passive fluency in context.

5.3. Understanding the meaning of foreign words out of context is an advanced phase of passive mastery of foreign vocabulary, where the ability to actively use foreign words in speaking or writing has not yet been developed. Although the words of this stage of

learning are not actively used, the degree of understanding is higher compared to the previous stage. At this stage, learners know their basic meaning. Understanding the meaning of foreign words out of context represents the second phase of the process of mastery of the foreign language. The degree of mastery of these words is passive mastery of foreign vocabulary encountered out of context.

Primary conclusion: The process of learning foreign words goes through several stages: recognizing words without understanding their meaning, understanding words in context, and finally, understanding words out of context. Initial recognition is important for forming correct pronunciation, while understanding words in context and out of context are advanced phases of passive foreign vocabulary acquisition. Implicit learning generally results in longer-term retention than explicit learning.

6. Processes for the Acquisition of Foreign Words

The process of acquiring foreign vocabulary represents the transformation of passive knowledge into active skills, i.e., passive, unused words become active, usable words.

6.1. Active utilization of foreign vocabulary, which encompasses its application in both speaking and writing. The active use of the foreign language is the fourth of the processes of mastering the foreign language, called the acquisition of the foreign language (language acquisition). This process transforms knowledge into skills. Recurring encounters with the foreign word in context can lead to transformation, but the most reliable method is through repeated active use in conversation or writing in the foreign language. These words have an active level of proficiency.

6.2. Perfect mastery of all meanings of foreign vocabulary (proficiency level), as well as speaking without an accent, as a first language. The level of proficiency in these words is active without or with a weak accent.

Primary conclusion: The process of acquiring foreign vocabulary consists of transforming passive knowledge into active skills through repeated use in speaking and writing. The goal is perfect mastery of the language, including all word meanings, and speaking without an accent like a native speaker.

7. Techniques for learning and acquiring a foreign language

Research should demonstrate the effectiveness of techniques used for learning and acquiring a foreign language. Only techniques that activate and stimulate the human mind to absorb and acquire foreign words and grammar can be effective. These techniques are natural and related to human nature. Of course, the use of technical means of teaching is also a good idea because it will increase the quality of teaching and, therefore, the degree of absorption of the learning material. A characteristic feature of learning and acquiring a foreign language is that they are two continuous processes that develop parallel to each other. One process can benefit from techniques designed for the other, and vice versa.

Listening and reading comprehension are both effective techniques for increasing vocabulary in passive memory. Listening comprehension is very useful in the initial period of learning a foreign language, and reading comprehension is useful in a more advanced phase of language acquisition. It is also useful for learning grammar, which is studied theoretically in parallel with a teacher. There is also another, less popular way of acquiring vocabulary: the repeated copying of foreign words. It is also possible to copy entire expressions to more easily assimilate and memorize the foreign vocabulary. The downside of this technique is that it is not without effort. Using flash cards with unknown words and their reversed translations is like this technique. All these techniques are beneficial for passive vocabulary development. Theoretically and practically, it is possible that a small percentage of the learned words pass into active memory.

Dialogue is an effective technique for increasing vocabulary in working memory. This method's unique feature allows the foreign language learner to benefit by incorporating the vocabulary of the other party into the conversation. Exercises with questions in which the learner answers out loud and can check the correctness of their answers are useful.

Video podcasts are especially useful because the pictures contribute to an easier understanding of the meaning of the vocabulary used. All these techniques are inherent to the natural process of learning a foreign language.

Primary conclusion: Effective techniques for learning and acquiring a foreign language include listening, reading, dialogue, and using technical means that encourage active language use. These methods are natural and help facilitate the smooth transition of passive knowledge into active skills.

8. Research

We conduct a long-term survey on the topic of the article using the Facebook.com platform. We have registered a Facebook group for foreign language learning for this purpose. [5]

Question asked:

“Which methods do you find most effective for memorizing foreign language words?”

We offered respondents 17 answers to choose from, allowing them to select more than one. 573 respondents took part in the survey and gave their preferences for the following answers:

- By actively using words, 24%
- By listening and reading the words in graded texts, 16%
- By repeating the words aloud, 10%

The survey validates the author's theory, which suggests that listening and reading are the most effective methods for expanding passive vocabulary. The survey also confirms that the best way to expand the active vocabulary is through the active use of foreign words and their repetition out loud.

Conclusion:

Learning and acquiring a foreign language is a complex and multifaceted process that requires both knowledge and skills. In this article, we have looked at

the basic principles, methods, and techniques that support this process. Vocabulary and grammar are foundational elements, but active language use and practical skills are essential to achieving foreign language proficiency.

The processes of passive and active acquisition of foreign vocabulary go through several phases, each of which is important for the overall mastery of the language. The article describes various methods and techniques that offer diverse approaches to foreign language learning, tailored to the individual needs of learners.

Despite significant advances in pedagogical methods and techniques, research in the field of language learning continues to provide new opportunities to improve the process. Future research could focus on integrating new technologies and methods for personalized

learning to meet learners' individual needs and learning styles.

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